

Features of Socio-Pedagogical Work with Gifted Children in Organizations of Supplementary Education

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Abstract

The work with gifted children, which is not only a state, but also a public responsibility, involves the issues of children's formation and development, and it is associated with the consideration of the most effective practices of social and pedagogical work with this substandard category.

In this regard, the aim of the article is to identify the peculiarities of social-pedagogical work with gifted children in organizations of supplementary education. The study represents the results of analyzing the questions of assistance for gifted children, the problem of gifted children's development in the context of social justice, and the review of the educationalists' attitudes to the effectiveness of socio-pedagogical work with gifted and talented children in supplementary educational organizations in the cities of Kursk and Kostroma.

The leading method of considering this problem is the questionnaire method conducted among 129 educators, which enables us to identify the features of socio-pedagogical work with gifted and talented children.

According to the results of the research, the peculiarities of social-pedagogical work with gifted children are specified in the comparative analysis of the educationalists' experiences in Kostroma and Kursk. Common and specific characteristics of the educationalists' work with this category of children are identified.

The identified features will allow to influence the organization of work with gifted and talented children in educational institutions of different types. The article findings emphasize the necessity of a psychologically comfortable creative environment in an institution of supplementary education.

Keywords: giftedness, gifted children, organization of supplementary education, educationalist.

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Published by Kazan federal university and peer-reviewed under responsibility of IFTE-2020 (VI International Forum on Teacher Education)

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Introduction

The priority direction of modern state policy is to support talented and gifted children as creative people who can find new solutions in the industrial and social spheres, who are able to set and solve the tasks of their own future and future of the country. In a number of normative acts of the Russian Federation, the importance of working with gifted children in educational organizations is emphasized, the need to provide equal opportunities for all categories of children is determined regardless of their capabilities. However educators do not fully take into account the specific features of the development of gifted children, they are not sufficiently aware of forms and methods of how to work with this category of children so the need is to identify the peculiarities of work with gifted children.

Purpose and objectives of the study

The purpose of the research is to identify the features of social-pedagogical work with gifted children in organizations of supplementary education.

Literature review

A number of scientists have studied the peculiarities of working with talented children. Among foreign works, the approaches of Eddles-Hirsch, Vialle, McCormick, and Rogers (2012), Hennessey (2004), Rogers (2007) are worthy of attention. The serious contribution to the study of the issue of children's giftedness is made by Bogoyavlenskaya (2004), Savenkov (2019), Yurkevich (2011).

In the working concept of giftedness, the definition of a gifted child is specified as a child with bright, obvious, and sometimes outstanding abilities (or has internal prerequisites for such achievements) in a particular type of activity (Bogoyavlenskaya, 2004).

Yurkevich defining the concept of "a gifted child" speaks about a child who has a high level of development of certain abilities and is distinguished by a high level of motivation for self-development and highly developed cognitive need (Yurkevich, 2011). The development of the potency among gifted children is reasonable and even vital for educational policy, which does not violate the equality in approaches to different categories of children, and it is based on a rational approach (Il'ina, 2015). So, within the Federal project "Success of every child" a unified system of measures, which are aimed at increasing children's motivation, revealing and developing their abilities and talents (such as multi-stage and multi-level contests, Olympiads and other events for children) is arranged. Moreover, there are

regional centers for identifying, supporting and developing skills and talents among children and young people on the basis of leading educational organizations (Popova, 2011).

In educational organizations of various types, including the system of supplementary education, special conditions must be created to promote efficiency in educational and socializing processes, which is the responsibility of the Federal State Educational Standard. It is important to note that among the current problems the following ones can be mentioned: the solution to problems with self-regulation, motivation, the search of life meanings, and attitude to oneself and others. Optimal conditions for personal and social development of gifted children should be created in organizations of supplementary education (Shcherbinina, 2019).

Methodology

The research methods and techniques: analysis of bibliographic data and compilation of empirical data which are carried out through interviewing the educationalists from organizations of supplementary education in Kostroma and Kursk.

Methodologically, the research is based on an activity approach that allows us to characterize the actions and efforts of educationalists, peers, and a gifted child in the subject-subject relationships. At the same time, our work is based on the regulations of a personality-oriented approach, which is aimed at creating conditions for gifted children to perceive themselves as individuals. This approach contributes to the formation of self-consciousness of gifted children, the development of self-identification and self-realization (Grushetskaya, & Shcherbinina, 2018).

Experimental base of the research: the municipal state-funded institution of supplementary education "Zhemchuzhina" (Kostroma), state budget institution of supplementary education Dvorec tvorchestva (Kostroma region), municipal state-funded institution of supplementary education "Zavolzhye" (Kostroma), municipal state-funded institution of supplementary education "Rovesnik" (Kostroma), municipal state-funded institution of supplementary education "Dvorec pionerov i shkolnikov" (Kursk).

Results

The results of the survey reveal that the experiences of the educationalists of supplementary education in Kostroma and Kursk, while conducting social and pedagogical work with gifted children, are similar. The pedagogic activity of the interviewed specialists is focused on developing the abilities of gifted children and maintaining work with them at different age stages. The pedagogues of multidisciplinary institutions of supplementary education work preferably with children who have creative, intellectual, artistic and social gifts.

According to the survey, gifted children are distinguished by broad erudition (68% - Kostroma, 66% - Kursk), high academic performance (38% and 59% - respectively), promptness of completion of educational tasks (63% and 67%, respectively), the tendency to leadership is marked by 54% and 32% of the surveyed Kostroma and Kursk pedagogues respectively.

The educationalists of Kursk depict high academic performance as a distinctive feature of gifted children. According to Kostroma pedagogues, gifted children are more likely to have conflicts and behave arrogantly (12% and 8%, respectively). Kostroma educationalists (17% and 12.5%, respectively) indicate inadequate self-esteem, 14% of Kostroma pedagogues and 8% of Kursk specialists mark the rejection of gifted children by their peers as a distinctive feature.

Figure 1. Distinctive qualities of gifted children

The educators do not always take into account the individual characteristics of gifted children. It should be mentioned that rejection of peers, inadequate self-esteem, conflicts in interaction are regarded as common characteristics of gifted children, however, a fairly low percentage of the interviewed educationalists depict these features of gifted children. The question is whether the pupils are treated in a fair way as it is necessary to take into account all personal characteristics which are not always taken in full.

The absolute majority of the pedagogues in Kostroma and Kursk (89% and 84% respectively) consider that their organizations deal with the problems of social-pedagogical work. While being interviewed, the educationalists regard identification, diagnostics and assistance of gifted children as conduction of the

socio-pedagogic work. The purpose of their programs is society adaptation, promotion of children's talent, as well as the development of gifted students. According to our opinion, the maintenance of programs, which draw attention to the question of adaptation of gifted children in the society and the environment of their peers and adults, brings advantages to talented children.

Moreover, the educationalists of the two regions give similar answers in choosing priority areas of work with gifted children. Kostroma pedagogues pay more attention to development of their skills (82%), promotion of the talent (78%), creation of conditions for self-development (78%) and assistance with self-identification (76%). Kursk educationalists emphasize such areas as help in self-development and promotion of talent (73% of the responses from the total number of respondents in each aspect), 71% of respondents determine the importance of developing abilities, 69% of the interviewees give priority to assistance with self-determination of a gifted child. However, only a third of the respondents (31% of the educationalists in Kursk and 34% - in Kostroma) depict the necessity of regular diagnostics of gifted children, whereas from 44% to 52% of the educationalists imply assistance with self-development and establishment of positive relationships.

Figure 2. Priority areas for working with gifted children

Thus regular diagnostics of gifted children, assistance with social development and establishment of positive interrelationships demonstrate the lowest percentage in the responses of the educationalists from the organizations of supplementary education. As for social justice in the psychological aspect of the term, it should be noted that every child regardless of individual abilities needs support even while establishing positive relationships with peers and adults (parents and teachers). The question arises whether the attention paid to gifted children is sufficient and their social and pedagogical support is provided in situations of social difficulties, their vulnerability, emotional instability, and in cases of conflicts.

The effectiveness of the educationalists' work in Kursk and Kostroma is maintained due to traditional and innovative forms of work with gifted children. The pedagogues from the organizations of supplementary education relate electives, creative associations, sections, gaming activities, competitions, Olympiads, contests to traditional forms. Individual and group consultations are gaining popularity. They include online consultations via the Internet, various messengers and chats, providing personal growth, professional self-determination, as well as admission of gifted children to specialized educational institutions.

According to the results of the survey among the educationalists, the major subject conducting social and pedagogical work with gifted children is represented by the specialists of supplementary education (100% of the responses from Kursk and Kostroma educationalists). More than 80% of Kursk and Kostroma pedagogues determine the importance of personality of an educational psychologist in working with gifted children. 62% of Kostroma and 52% of Kursk educationalists find the participation of a social pedagogue in working with gifted children necessary. The role of camp counselors and educators in working with gifted children is specified by 25% of Kursk pedagogues and 27% of Kostroma pedagogues; 24% of the interviewees in Kursk and Kostroma consider the participation of the deputy director (vice-principal) significant, and about 15% of all surveyed specialists see a relevant role of parents in working with gifted children.

It is necessary to stress that work with gifted children in the context of social justice should be conducted by a number of subjects, which provides the most complete systematic assistance for a gifted child in the area of supplementary education, as well as in other types of educational organizations.

Participation and victories of gifted children in contests and Olympiads (95%), educational results (60%), children's ability to communicate with each other (58%) are regarded by Kostroma educationalists as criteria of effectiveness in the socio-pedagogical work. Less percentage of responses from Kursk respondents is given to such work outcomes as skills to solve conflict situations (53%), friends and the ability of gifted children to work in pairs (36%). Kursk teachers specify the effectiveness of social and pedagogical work with the gifted in similar indicators, such as participation and victories of the gifted teenagers in contests and Olympiads (87.5%), children's educational results (63%), children's ability to communicate with each other (67%). The responses such as the ability to solve conflicts (51%), work in pairs (42%), friends (30%) are rarely chosen.

Significantly, admitting social justice into the process of work with gifted children, specialists of supplementary education should not only see academic results, creative and sportive achievements but also

form the ability to solve complex conflict situations within their classes and contribute to the development of harmonious interpersonal relationships.

As part of the social development of gifted children, the educationalists note a number of difficulties which are seen by about 60% of Kursk and Kostroma pedagogues. The main obstacles in social development are unstable self-esteem, difficulties in motivating talented children, excessive demands on themselves, unnecessary emotionality, spontaneity of decisions made, rejection by peers and teachers, difficulties in communication with peers and adults. In general, the teachers of Kursk and Kostroma demonstrate an eagerness to help with overcoming difficulties of the social development of gifted children. Among the main forms of assistance the educationalists detect a set of forms and methods of work in accordance with individual and age peculiarities of development, individual support of a child, assistance in adaptation in a collective, work with parents of gifted children, mentoring.

Thus, in our research, devoted to the study of practical experience of work with gifted children of the educationalists from the cities of Kostroma and Kursk, the peculiarities of professional socio-educational activity conducted in the two Russian cities are analyzed. The research reveals that the educationalists from Kostroma and Kursk organize socio-pedagogical work with gifted children and have a specific experience of socio-pedagogical activity. The educators from the two regions demonstrate similar views on the development of gifted children, the forms and methods of working with them, the difficulties of their social development. In general, they conduct their teaching activities within the framework of social justice, realizing the need for the success of each child.

Discussions

Peculiarities and difficulties in working with gifted children are characterized by several scientists and practitioners who conduct work with them. Thus, Savenkov (2019) remarks that the pedagogical assistance for gifted children commences with the identification of their personal characteristics, the level of intellectual development, the nature of creative abilities, interests and interpersonal relationships.

As part of the analysis, Yurkevich (2011) observes that the major object of research on gifted children is to identify adapting and socializing difficulties among such a category of children. According to the researcher, it is important to focus on the diagnosis of personal traits (anxiety, self-esteem, value orientations). Moreover, according to the author's opinion, there is a necessity in maintenance of educationalists' psychological and pedagogical competency which is aimed at improving knowledge and practical skills in work with gifted children.

The results of our empirical research enable us to say that for educationalists working with gifted children their personal achievements and successes, focused on the institution where they work with children, play a significant role. It seems valuable that the educators who work with this substandard category conduct their programs, taking into account personal characteristics of a gifted child, a type of giftedness, possible difficulties he or she faces, and provide complex assistance in personal and social development.

Conclusion

The obtained research data enable us to highlight some peculiarities of social-pedagogical work with gifted children in the system of supplementary education. The comparison of the information about professional activity of the educationalists specifies the content and objects of socio-pedagogical work with gifted children in organizations of supplementary education in the context of social justice. The article findings emphasize the necessity of a psychologically comfortable creative environment in an institution of supplementary education, as well as the presence of high psychological and pedagogical competency of a specialist of supplementary education and activation of children's work in pairs and groups.

The pointed peculiarities of work with gifted children, proven on the example of studying the experiences from the two cities, give an opportunity to influence the way work with gifted children and adolescents in educational organizations of supplementary education is arranged; and to analyze the issues of socio-pedagogical work with gifted children in the context of social justice.

Acknowledgements

The reported study was funded by RFBR according to the research project № 20-013-00656.

The theme of the grant «Difficulties of gifted children in solving tasks of socialization: causes of emergence and possibilities of overcoming».

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